

List of Technologies for Fairness Assessment in AI

This document contains all the technologies for fairness assessment in AI, along with their respective references, which we identified from a dataset of 213 technologies for AI ethics assessment developed and made available in Silva's master's research [1]. We organized the technologies in alphabetical order.

Technologies:

1. A confidence-based approach for balancing fairness and accuracy. <https://epubs.siam.org/doi/abs/10.1137/1.9781611974348.17>
2. A seven-layer model with checklists for standardising fairness assessment throughout the AI lifecycle' <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s43681-023-00266-9>
3. A toolkit of dilemmas: Beyond debiasing and fairness formulas for responsible AI/ML <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/10227133>
4. A Toolkit to Enable the Design of Trustworthy AI https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-90963-5_41
5. A3i the Trust in AI Framework <https://a3i.ai/>
6. Accenture Fairness Evaluation Tool <https://www.nist.gov/document/nist-ai-rfi-accenture-001pdf>
7. AI and Big Data: A blue print for a human rights, social and ethical impact assessment <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clsr.2018.05.017>
8. AI Fairness 360 <https://aif360.mybluemix.net/resources>
9. Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI) for self-assessment <https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/european-ai-alliance/pages/altai-assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence>
10. Auditing Algorithms: Research Methods for Detecting Discrimination on Internet Platforms <https://www.kevinhamilton.org/share/papers/Auditing%20Algorithms%20--%20Sandvig%20--%20ICA%202014%20Data%20and%20Discrimination%20Preconference.pdf>
11. BOLD: Dataset and Metrics for Measuring Biases in Open-Ended Language Generation <https://doi.org/10.1145/3442188.3445924>
12. Co-Designing Checklists to Understand Organizational Challenges and Opportunities around Fairness in AI <https://doi.org/10.1145/3313831.3376445>
13. Community jury <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/azure/architecture/guide/responsible-innovation/community-jury/>
14. Consequence Scanning <https://doteveryone.org.uk/project/consequence-scanning/>
15. Counterfactual fairness <https://arxiv.org/abs/1703.06856>
16. Data Statements for Natural Language Processing: Toward Mitigating System Bias and Enabling Better Science https://direct.mit.edu/tacl/article/doi/10.1162/tacl_a_00041/43452/Data-Statements-for-Natural-Language-Processing

17. Equity Evaluation Corpus (EEC)
<https://saifmohammad.com/WebPages/Biases-SA.html>
18. Fair, transparent, and accountable algorithmic decision-making processes: the premise, the proposed solutions, and the open challenges
<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s13347-017-0279-x>
19. Fairlearn: A toolkit for assessing and improving fairness in AI
https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/research/uploads/prod/2020/05/Fairlearn_WhitePaper-2020-09-22.pdf
20. Fairness Constraints: Mechanisms for Fair Classification
<http://proceedings.mlr.press/v54/zafar17a.html>
21. Fairness in Design: A Framework for Facilitating Ethical Artificial Intelligence Designs
https://www.scopus.com/record/display.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85158113243&origin=SingleRecordEmailAlert&dgcid=raven_sc_search_en_us_email&txGid=796db5a63807136db5ed2064f2ef043d
22. Fairness Score and process standardization: framework for fairness certification in artificial intelligence system
<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s43681-022-00147-7>
23. Human Decisions and Machine Predictions
<https://academic.oup.com/qje/article/133/1/237/4095198>
24. Improving Social Responsibility of Artificial Intelligence by Using ISO 26000
<https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1757-899X/428/1/012049>
25. Judgment Call
<https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/azure/architecture/guide/responsible-innovation/judgmentcall>
26. Judgment Call the Game: Using Value Sensitive Design and Design Fiction to Surface Ethical Concerns Related to Technology
<https://doi.org/10.1145/3322276.3323697>
27. Learning adversarially fair and transferable representations
<http://proceedings.mlr.press/v80/madras18a/madras18a.pdf>
28. Man is to computer programmer woman this homemaker?
<https://github.com/tolga-b/debiaswe>
29. People + AI Research <https://pair.withgoogle.com/>
30. Principles for accountable algorithms and a social impact statement for algorithms
<https://www.fatml.org/resources/principles-for-accountable-algorithms>
31. PROCAST: A Tool to Assess the Risk of Bias and Applicability of Prediction Model Studies
<https://doi.org/10.7326/M18-1376>
32. Questioning the assumptions behind fairness solutions
<https://arxiv.org/abs/1811.11293>
33. Responsible AI <https://www.tensorflow.org/resources/responsible-ai>
34. RESPONSIBLE AI LICENSES <https://www.licenses.ai/ai-licenses>
35. Responsible AI Toolbox <https://responsibleaitoolbox.ai/>
36. Responsible and Inclusive Technology Framework: A Formative Framework to Promote Societal Considerations in Information Technology Contexts
<https://arxiv.org/abs/2302.11565>

37. Responsible natural language processing: A principlist framework for social benefits
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2022.122306>
38. Ten simple rules for responsible big data research
<https://journals.plos.org/ploscompbiol/article?id=10.1371/journal.pcbi.1005399>
39. Tensorflow Fairness Indicators <https://github.com/tensorflow/fairness-indicators>
40. The Algorithmic Equity Toolkit (AEKit) <https://www.aclu-wa.org/AEKit>
41. The ICO and artificial intelligence: the role of fairness in the GDPR framework
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S026736491830044X?via%3Dihub>
42. The LinkedIn Fairness Toolkit (LiFT) <https://github.com/linkedin/LiFT>
43. Theyshallbefair, transparent, and robust: auditing learning analytics systems <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s43681-023-00292-7>
44. Three naïve Bayes approaches for discrimination-free classification
<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10618-010-0190-x>
45. Toward situated interventions for algorithmic equity: lessons from the field
<https://doi.org/10.1145/3351095.3372874>
46. UnBias fairness toolkit (version1). Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2667808>
47. Understanding artificial intelligence ethics and safety: A guide for the responsible design and implementation of AI systems in the public sector
<https://zenodo.org/record/3240529>
48. Weights & Biases <https://wandb.ai/site>
49. What-If Tool <https://pair-code.github.io/what-if-tool/>
50. When worlds collide: integrating different counterfactual assumptions in fairness.
https://proceedings.neurips.cc/paper_files/paper/2017/file/1271a7029c9df08643b631b02cf9e116-Paper.pdf

References

[1] SILVA, Jhésica Victória Santos da. Avaliação de ferramentas de ética em modelos de linguagem desenvolvidos em português. 2024. 1 recurso online (117 p.) Dissertação (mestrado) - Universidade Estadual de Campinas (UNICAMP), Instituto de Computação, Campinas, SP. Disponível em: <https://hdl.handle.net/20.500.12733/24297>. Acesso em: 5 jun. 2025.